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An Overview of the Pathophysiology of Major Depression: Neural Atrophy and Functional Dysregulation

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Rationale

Major depressive disorder (MDD) is best understood as a condition involving psychological, medical and social dimensions. It is in patients' best interest to enable better public understanding of the fact that clinical depression is not solely confined to the subjective experience level but has a visible, measurable neurobiological substrate. For some, a more concrete idea of the disorder may help in grasping the reality of the functional impairments patients report.

Over the past two or more decades, converging evidence from structural and functional neuroimaging and molecular neuroscience has revealed depression's objective signature in **brain architecture**. These findings reinforce the seriousness of the disorder and that the subjective experience is reflected in physical brain changes.

This article provides an overview of the most relevant changes in brain tissue structure and connectivity that are associated with depression.

Hippocampal Volume Reduction in MDD

Large-scale neuroimaging meta-analyses confirm that depressed patients have significantly lower hippocampal volumes than controls. In the ENIGMA consortium analysis, more than 1,700 MDD patients were examined, with recurrent patients showing ~1.44% smaller hippocampi (Cohen's $d = -0.14$) and early-onset MDD (≤ 21 years) showing ~1.85% with $d = -0.2$. Multiple depressive episodes or longer illness durations have shown to modulate hippocampal atrophy in MDD.

A magnitude of 4-10% in severe or longstanding cases (but smaller clinical studies) could be observed, showing that longer cumulative depression leads to progressive hippocampal injury. While 1-2% reflects the typical case magnitude, the upper end of 4-10% is quite disturbing.

In ENIGMA, the authors mention associations between smaller hippocampal volume as predicting poorer treatment outcomes, and since the hippocampus is associated with context processing and memory, reduced volume can be associated with correlates in memory impairment and executive deficits. Contextualization processing is one major concern in MDD, making it hard (or impossible) for patients to accurately place different sorts of experiences in context.

Schmaal et al. (2016) | McKinnon et al. (2009) | Sheline et al. (1999) | MacQueen & Frodl (2011) | Sheline et al. (2003) | Videbech & Ravnkilde (2004) | MacMaster & Kusumakar (2004)

Cortical Thinning

Adults with MDD show small but significant reduced cortical thickness in gray matter in frontal and insular brain regions, particularly in the orbitofrontal cortex, the anterior cingulate cortex (located in the medial frontal lobe), the insula and the lateral temporal cortex (magnitude $\sim d = -0.1 - -0.14$). While modest, the findings are highly consistent across 20 cohorts. Other findings include a significant thinning in right lateral hemisphere regions of around .87mm, reflecting a reduction of 28% when there is a family history of depression. Although the direct links between cortical thinning and genetic predisposition, symptom severity and variety and treatment response are not fully established, the findings clearly suggest significant connections.

Frontal cortical atrophy plausibly relates to executive deficits in emotional regulation and general cognitive control – these are

regularly significantly impaired in MDD. Besides that, dorsolateral and orbitofrontal thinning and ACC volume has been associated with difficulties in decision-making, impaired concentration, apathy and general cognitive slowing.

Peterson et al. (2009) | Schmaal et al. (2017) | Mackin et al. (2013) | Li et al. (2025)

Prefrontal Cellular Pathophysiology

MDD patients show reduced neuronal soma size and reduced glial cell density in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the ACC. These changes correspond to impaired regulation of mood (due to loss of support cells), executive deficits and impairment in 'rational' thinking. In Brodmann Area 9 (dorsolateral PFC) and the orbitofrontal cortex of MDD patients, when compared to healthy controls, neuronal size and density is decreased in the upper cortical layers, with a magnitude of around 20-30%.

In the subgenual ACC (Brodmann area 25) glial density has been found reduced by ~22% and neuron soma size by ~23% in layer IV patients, with confirmed statistical significance. It can furthermore be reasonably assumed that glial support loss (astrocytes and oligodendrocytes) impair synaptic functioning, namely in mood regulation and cognitive processing (slow). Smaller PFC neurons indicate significant atrophy of dendrites or synaptic loss, which corresponds with neuroimaging findings of reduced prefrontal activity in MDD.

Rajkowska et al. (1999) | Cotter et al. (2002) | Koolschijn et al. (2009) | Wang, H. (2022) | Gittins & Harrison (2011) | Czeh & Nagy (2018)

Diffuse Loss in White Matter Microstructure Integrity

Fractional anisotropy (FA) is reduced in white matter in MDD. FA is a measure derived from Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI) quantifying the direction and degree of water molecule diffusion: high FA indicates good fiber integrity (density), axonal diameter and healthy myelination.

Loss of integrity basically means a less efficient communication network. ENIGMA data reported significantly reduced FA (Cohen's d 0.12 to 0.26) in 16 out of 25 major tracts. Especially affected are the corpus callosum, corona radiata and the cingulum bundle, with the most significant of them being the corpus callosum (the main nerve fiber bundle connecting both hemispheres) and the anterior corona radiata, a frontal projection pathway. Notably, these findings were only observed in adult patients and not in adolescents. White matter disruption leads to what patients describe as 'brain fog' and which might possibly be psychomotor retardation due to inefficient neural conduction.

Furthermore, previous studies yielded findings of fractional anisotropy in white matter in the right frontal lobe, right fusiform gyrus, left frontal lobe and right occipital lobe. Subsequent fiber tracking specifically highlighted the right inferior longitudinal fasciculus, right inferior fronto-occipital fasciculus, right posterior thalamic radiation and interhemispheric fibres running through the genu and body of the corpus callosum.

Liao et al. (2013) | Chen et al. (2016) | van Velzen et al. (2020)

Amygdala Hyperreactivity and Elevated Perfusion

Patients with MDD have an overactive amygdala response to negative stimuli. The amygdala's baseline activity (e.g., perfusion and glucose metabolism) correlates positively with symptom severity in clinical depression. The amygdala's role is important in the body's emotional processing, especially in stressful events. It sends distress signals to the hypothalamus, which acts like a command center, activating the sympathetic nervous system through sending the signal through the autonomous nerves to the adrenal glands. These glands release epinephrine in the bloodstream triggering a cascade of effects in the body that we typically associate with the immediate feeling of stress ('fight or flight' response).

It is a scientifically robust finding that amygdala overactivity is a core feature in clinically depressed individuals, reinforced by many neuroimaging studies. Clinically, this corresponds strongly to the hypervigilance and negative bias in depressive disorder, as well as the general emotional over-reactivity.

Meta-analyses have shown general greater responses to negative stimuli of the amygdala, dACC and insula in MDD, but lower responses of the dorsal striatum and the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex. Furthermore, structural connectivity loss, similarly to HPC-PFC (see below) was found in amygdala-PFC.

LeWine (2024) | Drevets et al. (2008) | Weidacker et al. (2021) | Siegle et al. (2007) | Barreiros et al. (2024) | Ho et al. (2019) | Hamilton et al. (2012) | Tang et al. (2013)

Reward Processing in the Ventral Striatum

Depression features hypoactivation in the nucleus accumbens. The NAcc, a cluster of neurons and the largest structure contained within the ventral striatum, integrates inputs from the limbic system and modulates motivated behaviors, experience of pleasure and reward. It is a critical hub in the brain's reward circuitry.

Blunted striatal activation (especially NAcc) when receiving or even expecting potential rewards corresponds directly with what

Diminished striatal activation (especially NAcc) when receiving or even expecting potential rewards corresponds directly with what is commonly termed anhedonia, the inability to experience pleasure. Furthermore, the loss of interest in rewarding activities and the general lack of motivation, which are hallmarks of depressive symptoms, strongly correspond with the anhedonic deficit in striatal response in the brain. The reported loss of a rewarding feeling of positive events mirrors the reduced NAcc activation, exactly as the substantially lessened expenditure of effort for rewards reflects the significant reduction of signals for reward anticipation. Dysregulated corticostriatal connectivity has been named an empirical foundation for an understanding of abnormalities in the reward circuitry, mirroring the anhedonic experience and behavior in clinically depressed individuals.

Keren et al. (2018) | Ng et al. (2019) | Halahakoon et al. (2020) | Pizzagalli et al. (2009) | Yang et al. (2022) | Hamilton et al. (2012)

Subgenual Anterior Cingulate Cortex Abnormalities

The subgenual anterior cingulate cortex (sgACC, Brodmann area 25) shows abnormally elevated resting metabolic activity and perfusion at baseline in clinical depression. In unmedicated patients, positron emission tomography (PET) often shows the sgACC as a 'hot spot' of resting glucose metabolism and blood flow, therefore BA25 is often referred to as the 'sadness center' among researchers.

The finding that sgACC metabolism correlates strongly positively with depressive symptom severity has not only been replicated many times, but also, the treatment-based reduction of sgACC hyperactivity correlates with clinical improvement. This dual correlation strengthens the connection between MDD and the sgACC.

In adolescent MDD patients, so called RSFC (resting state functional connectivity) between the sgACC and insula and amygdala has also been found elevated, whereas significantly *decreased* connectivity could be observed between sgACC and precuneus, again strongly correlating with the symptom severity. In addition to that, responders to SSRI treatment show normalized baseline activity, whereas non-responders show no change; obviously, in either, symptom severity and sgACC activity.

Connolly et al. (2013) | Hamilton et al. (2012) | Drevets et al. (1997) | Drevets et al. (2008) | Mayberg et al. (2005) | Holtzheimer et al. (2017) | Crowell et al. (2019) | Mayberg et al. (2000)

Region-Specific CBF Patterns

There is not a global uniform change pattern, but **MDD patients have consistently shown abnormalities in region-specific cerebral blood flow (rCBF).** In particular, frontal and cingulate regions tend to show hypoperfusion in resting state.

Decreased perfusion and metabolism in frontal regions, especially the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the dorsal anterior cingulate, correspond with executive dysfunction and emotional control and impulse control dysfunction. These are in line with the commonly observed symptoms in MDD, correlating with the assumption that frontal brain areas do not work as they should in depressive disorder.

The inability to initiate or complete daily routines, which is one of the hallmark symptoms of depression, can be framed as a cognitive-behavioral deficit, of which the strong correlation with frontal hypoperfusion is not a surprise at all.

When looked at in a more granular level, the dorsofrontal region is thought to be involved mainly in cognitive aspects of negative emotions such as apathy and impaired attention, whereas the ventral part mediates the vegetative aspects, such as circadian rhythms and appetite – both are known to be disturbed as typical symptom palette in depressive disorder.

The subgenual PFC shows hyperperfusion in MDD, corresponding with higher levels of negative rumination. The general tendency to engage in a high level of negative self-reflection and the inability to disengage from negative thinking spirals is one of the most common symptoms in MDD, and is likely connected to over- / underactivity of specific regions.

As discussed, there is not only hypoperfusion but also hyperperfusion and hypermetabolism, specifically in the amygdala and the sgACC. The key point is that there is not a uniform perfusion pattern that describes the pathophysiology of MDD, but consistently, there are alterations that manifest in the symptom domain.

It is currently thought that elevated perfusion patterns in the brain are directly linked to pathogenic hypermetabolism in specific regions with their magnitude reflected in the severity of symptoms. That means that region-specific higher blood flow connects to the higher consumption of glucose in the respective regions, corresponding with more severe symptoms the higher the overactivity.

In sum, MDD patients significantly differ from healthy controls in rCBF in executive, affective and motor networks.

Levy-Cooperman et al. (2008) | Peterson et al. (2024) | Hamilton et al. (2016) | Ho et al. (2013) | Ho et al. (2019) | Vasic et al. (2015) | Chen et al. (2015) | Gangl et al. (2023) | Lau et al. (2013) | Yan et al. (2019)

Neuroinflammation (Elevated TSPO Binding)

Positron emission tomography studies revealed significantly higher TSPO (18 kDa Translocator protein) binding in MDD patients' brains in multiple regions. PET scans measure neuroinflammation through a radioligand that binds to TSPO to reveal

the activation of glial cells. In a healthy brain, TSPO expression is very low and restricted mainly to endothelial and resting glial cells. In response to injury, disease or infection, TSPO is significantly upregulated.

Heightened TSPO binding is a reliable marker for neuroinflammation, and in MDD patients' brains, there could be observed an ~18% increase, however, examinations showed no clear correlation with depression severity, whereas other studies associate it with more severe symptoms. It should also be mentioned that some studies have only found elevated TSPO levels in about a third of examined patients. This means that not every depressed patient has high microglial activation. Those who do, however, are associated with treatment resistance to conventional antidepressants.

Breit (2025) | Hassamal (2023) | Setiawan et al. (2015) | Han & Ham (2021) | Eggerstorfer et al. (2022) | Meyer et al. (2020)

Fronto-Hippocampal Functional Connectivity Deficits

There is **considerable evidence that MDD patients suffer structural connectivity loss between the hippocampus and the prefrontal cortex**. Circuit abnormality between these two areas has been extensively researched and findings consistently show that communication between them is suboptimal in depression.

The fornix, which is the major white matter tract connecting the HPC to the PFC region, showed significantly lower fractional anisotropy in both diffusion tensor imaging and resting state fMRI studies. Bilateral HPC was affected in combination with left and right ventral PFC, and bilateral ventral / dorsolateral PFC. Also, fornix FA in healthy controls correlates negatively with functional connectivity between HPC and PFC, which was not seen in MDD patients. In non-remitting MDD patients, medial fornix FA was 19.2% lower in comparison to healthy controls.

While the hippocampus is critical for the emotional connection of memories, dysfunction leads to biased recall of negatively attributed memories. In MDD, neurotoxic events reduce its volume.

Risk factors for the development of depression, such as early-life stress and trauma have also been linked to smaller hippocampal volume, as well as disorders that have been linked to them, like e.g., dissociative identity disorder. In the latter, hippocampal volume was decreased by an average of around 20%.

Studies could also establish correlations between weaker connectivity between the right hippocampus and symptom severity, while generally, frontal-subcortical connections were significantly reduced.

Chalavi et al. (2015) | Geng et al. (2016) | Hoogenboom et al. (2014) | van Velzen et al. (2020) | Cao et al. (2012)

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